

RELIGIOUS FREEDOM AND ROMANIAN ADVENTISM IN THE PERIOD 1870-1946¹

Pastor Mihai STOICESCU, Ph.D.

Prof. LTA Ștefan Demetrescu, Bucharest

mihaystoicescu@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: Religious Freedom and Romanian Adventism in The Period 1870-1946.²

The end of the 19th century corresponded to the propagation of the Adventist message in the Romanian space. As ideas do not consider borders, both Little Romania (Wallachia, Moldova and Dobrogea) and the other Romanian provinces (Transylvania, Banat and Bukovina) were confronted with the Advent message through foreign preachers. Not without difficulties, this message penetrated the population, leading to the emergence of Romanian Adventism.

Keywords: *Adventist, Adventist history, religious freedom, human rights, freedom.*

Adventism originated in the early second half of the 19th century, following the spiritual revival movements in the United States of America. The message that united the believers was the imminent return of Christ, which they began to preach. Based on this belief, but also that related to the seventh-day Sabbath, the name Seventh-day Adventist was adopted. One by one, following biblical study, all Adventist beliefs were accepted.

Faithful to the biblical message of spreading the Gospel, the church encouraged missionary work both locally and abroad. Thus, in the second half of the 19th century, Adventism penetrated Europe and of course Romania. The Advent message took deep roots in the Romanian space and

1 This article is part of the undersigned's doctoral thesis *Dynamics of Financial Resources and Giving in the History of the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Romania*, defended in September 2023.

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despite all the difficulties caused by the two world wars and communism, it developed more than anywhere else in Europe.³ The message regarding the Sabbath was not foreign to the Romanian space, one of the Adventist missionaries arriving in Transylvania to seek the Sabbatarian movement, which can be said to have been the precursor of Romanian Adventism.

The Sabbatarian Movement

During the Protestant Reformation in the 16th century, in Transylvania many individuals and church leaders easily changed both their religion and nationality, for various reasons, but without any coercion.⁴ Against this background, the Sabbatarian movement appears within the Unitarian Church, considered by some authors to be the last reform of the 16th century.⁵

The German Reformed preachers Adam Neuser and Matthias Veche-Glirius are considered the promoters of this movement. However, in Transylvania, Sabbatarianism did not penetrate the hearts of the people through theological scholars, but through persecuted laypeople.⁶ Sabbatarians were anti-trinitarian, awaiting the Messiah who had not yet come to earth, and emphasizing the Sabbath, feasts, and dietary regulations. Although they closely resembled Judaism, they still considered circumcision to be a transitory commandment.

The Sabbatarian movement in Transylvania endured for four centuries.⁷ Constantly persecuted, especially under the Catholic Habsburg Empress Maria Theresa, the believers were often forced to formally return to

3 Gary Land, *Historical Dictionary of the Seventh-day Adventists*, in *Historical Dictionaries of Religions, Philosophies, and Movements*, No. 56 (Lanham, Maryland: The Scarecrow Press, 2005), 252.

4 Ladislaus M. Pákozdy, *Der siebenbürgische Sabbatismus. Seine Entstehung und Entwicklung vom Unitarismus zum Judentum sowie sein Untergang* (Stuttgart: Kohlhammer, 1973), 13.

5 Robert Dán, *Matthias Veche-Glirius, Life and Work of a Radical Antitrinitarian with his Collected Writings* (Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó; Leiden: E.J. Brill, 1982), 148-149.

6 Corneliu-Ghiocel Fitzai, *Mișcarea adventistă de ziua a șaptea din România* (Pantelimon: Viață și Sănătate, 2018), 81-82.

7 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, *Sabatarieni în contextul vieții transilvănene (sec. XVI-XX). Aspecte din Istoria Sabatarianismului european și transilvănean*, second edition revised and added, vol. II (Cluj-Napoca: Risoprint, 2019), 293-297.

the traditional churches. Finally, starting in 1866, against the background of granting Jews the same rights as all other citizens, Catholic, Reformed and Unitarian Sabbatarians converted to Judaism,⁸ except for a small religious group led by József Sallós. However, even this group was assimilated with the Jews, so that the vast majority ended up in fascist concentration camps. Those who managed to survive the camp continued the Sabbatarian movement until its disappearance around 1870-1880.⁹

It should be noted that, not even four years after the disintegration of the Sabbatarian movement, the Romanian space is confronted with the Advent message, through missionaries from America. The message regarding the Sabbath begins to be preached again, this being the common element between the Transylvanian Sabbatarian movement and Adventism.

The Pitesti Group

In Romanian territories, Adventism can be found in the Pitesti group, among the German colonists in Dobrogea, in Transylvania and Bucharest.

The Pitesti group was founded by the Polish-born Adventist missionary Michael (Michal) Belina Czechowski. The group developed through the magazine *Les Signes du Temps* published in Switzerland, in French. The group had 20 members, and they shamed the Jews for closing their shops on Saturday. The group was visited by the Italian missionary Bertola, who would baptize several more people.¹⁰

Toma Aslan writes to the editors of *Les Signes du Temps* informing them that the group has received the Advent message regarding the return and the Sabbath. Toma Aslan also states that everything discussed in the magazine corresponds to his faith. At the end of the letter, he provides some details about the group. It had 13 members and had a few friends in the truth. Some members kept the Sabbath rigorously and he believed that all would soon do so.¹¹ The letter was published in the February 1881 issue

8 Corneliu-Ghiocel Fitzai, *Mișcarea adventistă de ziua a șaptea din România*, 90-91.

9 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, „Soarta sabbatarienilor transilvăneni care nu au trecut în anul 1866 la credința iudaică,” *Studia Universitatis Babeș-Bolyai – Theologia Orthodoxa* 16.2 (2014): 119-134.

10 H. P. Ribton, “Report from Egypt,” *Review and Herald* 55.1 (1880): 13.

11 Dumitru Popa, *Biografii ale pionierilor Bisericii adventiste din România*, Vol. I (Bucharest: Grafix Print, 1995), 295.

and shows that the group had declined in numbers since Bertola's visit. On the other hand, these details show that the group here was not necessarily associated with the Adventist Church organizationally, but rather doctrinally. In fact, the group was practically following Czechowski's line of thinking. The important thing was the message, not the organization.

Also in 1881, Toma Aslan wrote another letter to *Les Signes du Temps*, along with several small brochures in Romanian.¹² As a result of this correspondence, Toma Aslan was invited to participate in the tenth session of the General Conference of Adventists in Europe, which took place in Basel, Switzerland, from October 19 to 23, 1883. Toma Aslan proved to be more than just a participant, as he requested the publication of a magazine in Romanian to spread the Advent message in Romania. Starting with 1884 and until 1888, the quarterly magazine *Adevărulu Present* was published, whose main editor and translator was Toma Aslan. The magazine was produced in Basel, the first issue causing great joy to the European Adventist mission.¹³

After the Basel Conference and the decision to print a magazine in Romanian, the group in Pitești received two visits from the church. The first was made by the president of the General Conference at that time, George Butler. Although he confessed that the decision to visit Romania was made with difficulty, due to the great distance and the high cost, the decision to print a magazine in Romanian mattered the most. The visit lasted four days, accompanied by Pastor Whitney and his niece, Edith Andrews, who facilitated the translation from English to French. At that time, the group consisted of seven members and a consistent number of interested persons. The seven members came from the upper echelons of society, composed of intelligent, sensitive and responsible people. Butler then relates how Czechowski formed this group and Toma Aslan's experience of drawing close to God, as well as the trials he went through regarding his faith, following the loss of his business due to the war between Romania and Turkey.¹⁴ He noted that although there was little interest in religion among the population, there was nevertheless an interest among the par-

12 Dumitru Popa, *Biografii ale pionierilor Bisericii adventiste din România*, Vol. I, 296.

13 B. L. Whitney, "Progress of the Cause. Report from Central European Mission," *Review and Herald* 61.1 (1884): 5.

14 George Butler refers to the Romanian War of Independence of 1877.

ticipants in the truth. This fact was also accentuated by the fact that the Bible was not read as it was in America. Therefore, Butler did not expect a large percentage of the Romanian population to receive the truth. However, he believed that there were valuable people who would accept it. Therefore, he confessed that this group needed pastoral assistance and why not a Romanian-speaking pastor.¹⁵ Butler had arrived in Romania for Easter and found a population wearing turbans and sandals. He also noticed that there were many Gypsies, some even darker than Native Americans.¹⁶

Butler's remark was put into effect, and Pastor A. C. Bourdeau was sent to Pitesti. In August, the group had only three members, all Armenians and with a great interest in working for those of the same nationality as them. Even the three needed help in correctly understanding the truth and even in observing the Sabbath, considering that they were ignorant of the Sabbath. The organization of the Church at Pitesti was now taking place, although the group had existed before that time, without the specific organization of the church. After holding over 50 public conferences, some of them with hundreds of participants, by August eight people had been baptized and six more were to be baptized. The magazine *Adevărulu Present* was circulating quite well, and they were preparing to give lectures in another city located about 60 miles from Pitesti, without being identified.¹⁷ In November a new report is published, stating that three more people have been baptized and four more are to follow. They have given up jewelry, wine, tobacco, tea, or mouse. They enjoy family worship, and appreciate worship and the Sabbath, as well as social and prayer meetings. The Sabbath School provides instruction and courage to the participants. We also learn from this that, together with Toma Aslan, Butler visited the cities of Bucharest and Ploiesti for a few days. As a result of these visits, several people expressed a desire to read more about the truth. It also seems that more people from various Romanian territories were subscribing to the magazine, and the reactions of the readers were extremely positive.¹⁸

15 George Butler, "Visit to Roumania," *Review and Herald* 61.21 (1884): 328-329.

16 George Butler, "Foreign Travel – No. 14. Roumania," *Youth's Instructor* 32.34 (1884): 134-135.

17 A. C. Bourdeau, "Progress of the Cause. Roumania," *Review and Herald* 61.39 (1884): 620.

18 A. C. Bourdeau, "Progress of the Cause. Roumania," *Review and Herald* 61.45 (1884): 715-716.

A few years later, Bourdeau published new details about his time in Romania. He began preaching in the Aslan family's living room, which could accommodate 40-50 people. Interest being very high, he moved to a family warehouse, where hundreds or even thousands of people could attend. He received permission from the prefect to gather there and began the series of presentations on a Sunday evening, an event that was attended by thousands of participants. On one of the evenings, there were also three Orthodox priests in the room who reacted vocally, requiring the intervention of the police so that Bourdeau could leave the room, because people were waiting for him outside with stones in their pockets. After the event, the authorities informed him that he would be expelled from the country the next day, but after a new meeting with the prefect, the meetings continued only in the Aslan family's living room. Regarding the presentations in Ploiesti and Bucharest, Bourdeau specifies that he was in Bucharest between two visits to Ploiesti. Interestingly, in Ploiesti, the missionary had a meeting with King Carol I, the latter being very kind, the conversation taking place in French to the amazement of those present. Bourdeau also states that Toma Aslan, who spoke five languages fluently, was appointed presbyter of the church in Pitesti and that he accompanied Bourdeau to Italy, to become better acquainted with the missionary's work, so that he could continue the activity begun in Pitesti.¹⁹

From another publication, published in 1885, we learn that A. C. Bourdeau was responsible for the mission in Romania.²⁰ Also, in 1884, 23,000 copies of *Adevărulu Present* were printed, and it was estimated that a third of these were distributed.²¹ Another interesting aspect is that Toma Aslan appears on the list of assistant pastors until 1888.²² Starting with 1889, Aslan no longer appears on the list of pastors, nor does he provide

19 A. C. Bourdeau, "Beginning of Our Work in Roumania," *European Division Conference Review* 2.2 (1913): 34-36.

20 "General Directories," *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook* 1885 (Battle Creek, MI: Seventh-day Adventist Publishing Association), 9.

21 "General Conference Proceedings," *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook* 1885, 21-22.

22 "Ministers Directory," *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook* 1885, 8. See and "Ministers Directory," *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook* 1886 (Battle Creek, MI: Seventh-day Adventist Publishing Association), 10; "Ministers Directory," *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook* 1887 (Battle Creek, MI: Seventh-day Adventist Publishing Association), 9; "Ministers Directory," *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook* 1888 (Battle Creek, MI: Seventh-day Adventist Publishing Association), 7.

information about the functioning of a community. The only detail specified is that there are three Sabbath keepers in Romania.²³ Starting with the following year, no more information appears regarding the Pitesti group or any Sabbath keeper. Romania is no longer listed as a member of the Central European Conference, indicating that the group finally disbanded.

Although the information about the Pitești group ends here, Adventism does not disappear from Romania. The Aslan family will move to Bucharest, and the work had to be rebuilt elsewhere, on a completely different foundation.²⁴

Dobrogea

The Advent message had reached the German communities in the Crimean Peninsula through publications. They had become interested in the message following conversations with ethnic Germans settled in America and who had become Adventists. In 1866, Conradi visited the German communities in Crimea and founded a community. About 30 years later, more precisely in 1890, the Russian authorities no longer renewed the leases of the Sabbatarian Germans, on the grounds that they kept the Sabbath and worked on Sundays. As a result, six families, including the church elder, arrived in Dobrogea, where the Romanian authorities offered them land to build their houses. Because they were not allowed to form their own colony, they settled on the outskirts of the town of Sarighiol,²⁵ near the ethnic Turks. They attracted the attention of other Germans because they were working on Sunday and complained to the authorities.²⁶

23 "General Conference Proceedings," *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook 1889* (Battle Creek, MI: Seventh-day Adventist Publishing Association), 74.

24 L. R. Conradi, "Begginings of Our Works in Europe," *Adventist Review Anniversary Issue* 101.38 (1924): 14.

25 Today Albesti, the locality near the city of Mangalia.

26 Ethnic Germans arrived in Dobrogea in three waves: 1841-1856; 1873-1883; 1890-1891. The first settlers, coming from the Leipzig area and parts of Warsaw, settled in Macin, then in the commune of Mircea Voda, Tulcea, becoming the first German colony in Dobrogea. They were followed by settlers from the Russian regions of Bassarabia (territory annexed to Russia at that time) and Kherson. Those in the second wave arrived in Suebia, a province in southern Germany. The third wave was represented by settlers from Crimea, among whom were Adventist Germans. The German community in Dobrogea was quite large and was located in localities such as Constanta (Neue Weingärten – Viile Noi district), Tulcea, Ciucurova, Cogealac, Mihail Kogalniceanu,

To their surprise, the police did not react because the Adventists did not drink alcohol, had the most beautiful households and there was no crime. The conclusion of the local authorities was that their religion was good and desirable, considering the results.

A year after their settlement in Dobrogea, they will be visited by Conradi. From the report written on this occasion, we learn that he wanted to travel to Syria, but upon arriving in Constantinople he learns that no ship can dock in any Syrian port because of cholera. Therefore, he comes to Dobrogea to visit the group of Adventists from Sarighiol, in the fall of 1891. At that time, Romania had been ruled by a prince from the house of Hohenzollern since 1866, had gained its independence in 1877 and had proclaimed itself a kingdom in 1881. Conradi notes that, at that time, Romania was slightly larger than the state of New York and had about the same population. Dobrogea had belonged to the Turks until 1878 and was about half the size of Maryland, with a population of about 120,000 people. After the war, the Romanian authorities encouraged Germans to settle in Dobrogea. This is how the brothers from Crimea arrived here. They were happy to see Conradi again and during the six days they organized a series of lectures. As a result, four new Germans decided to observe the Sabbath. They lived in Kalash-Kula,²⁷ and were also visited by Conradi.²⁸ During this time, a church consisting of 18 people was organized.²⁹

Before leaving for home, the missionary comes to Bucharest, with the aim of meeting with Toma Aslan, whom he had learned had moved there. Unfortunately, this did not happen.

The group from Sarighiol will benefit from the work of an American missionary of German origin, A. Wagner. He arrives in Sarighiol in 1892, the result being visible in the revival that occurs among the Lutherans. In a short time, 20 of them receive baptism, which caused a reaction among the other Lutherans. After only six months of his arrival, the number of members reached over 40.³⁰ Therefore, an attempt was made to remove

Atmagea (the most important Protestant center), Murfatlar, Cobadin, Costinesti, Tari-verde, Faclia, Albesti, Palazu Mare or Malcoci. Most of them left Romania in 1940.

27 There were many Germans on the border between Romania and Bulgaria, so it is possible that the town of Kalash-Kula was part of today's Cadrilater, Bulgaria.

28 L. R. Conradi, "A Visit to Rumania," *Review and Herald* 69.2 (1892): 25-26.

29 L. R. Conradi, "A Visit to Rumania," *Review and Herald* 71.20 (1894): 308.

30 L. R. Conradi, "A Visit to Rumania," *Review and Herald* 71.20 (1894): 308.

Wagner from the village, and he was notified by the authorities to leave the town within 10 days. Trusting in God, the missionary stayed. He consulted a lawyer who assured him that he would receive citizenship, but this did not happen. Things degenerated when two of the Adventists were beaten by Lutherans, and the case eventually reached the authorities. Under these conditions, Conradi returned to Dobrogea, to Sarighiol. Here he baptized four people, a fact that came to the attention of the authorities. After long attempts to discuss with the Romanian authorities or the American consul, they remained without any result. Conradi leaves Romania, after managing to meet with Toma Aslan.³¹ He told her that there was only one sister who still observed the Sabbath and that in Basel, Switzerland, only the brochure *What Day and Why?* was still printed in Romanian.³²

Conradi returned to Romania a year later. He managed to meet with the American consul, who gave him a letter of recommendation for the Minister of Religions and Education, Take Ionescu.³³ The discussion took place in a cordial atmosphere, conducted in English, and ended favorably for both the missionary Wagner and Conradi. Wagner received permission to return to Dobrogea, and Conradi the right to preach freely anywhere in Romania. Upon leaving, Conradi gave him *Steps to Christ* and other brochures he had on hand, for which the minister respectfully thanked him. At the same time, he had several conversations with Toma Aslan regarding the progress of the truth at that time. Aslan confessed to him that he would try to change his position, so that both he and his wife would respect the Sabbath again. Together they set up the distribution of some publications in Romanian. To this end, they contacted a prestigious printing house in Bucharest and Aslan introduced him to a translator, who would take care of translating all the materials into Romanian. They also planned to bring a missionary to Galați because it was near the Russian border.³⁴ Plans began to take shape, and that year a series of meetings were held that aroused

31 L. R. Conradi, "The Dragon's Voice in Rumania," *Review and Herald* 70.32 (1893): 506-507.

32 L. R. Conradi, "A Visit to Rumania," *Review and Herald* 71.20 (1894): 308.

33 Initially, Conradi had a discussion with his wife, Bessie Richard, an English Protestant, who asked her husband to give Conradi a letter guaranteeing his right to preach freely in Romania, by virtue of the religious freedoms that were recognized. See L. R. Conradi, "The Evening Sermon," *General Conference Bulletin* 9.13 (1922): 318.

34 L. R. Conradi, "A Visit to Rumania," *Review and Herald* 71.20 (1894): 308-309.

interest, and several people were baptized. The first booklet, *The Full Assurance of Faith*, was also printed in Bucharest.³⁵ The translator of these materials, who was Orthodox, began to become increasingly interested in the Bible, confessing that until then he had known and understood little.³⁶

It seems that Thomas Aslan and his wife began to observe the Sabbath again. Following Henry P. Holser's visit to Bucharest, he reports that he met with Aslan, who confessed to him that both he and his wife still remembered the visits of Butler and Whitney, as well as the work of Bourdeau. They also visited the only sister who had remained faithful to Sabbath observance from the beginning.³⁷ Two aspects are notable in this account. First, there is no mention of Czechowski, although Aslan received the Advent message from him. Second, the language used shows that the sister was not the only one who kept the Sabbath but was the only one who kept it from the beginning, a sign that the Aslans had reconsidered their position.

Over time, Adventism spread to Dobrogea, with a group of 52 people, made up of ethnic Germans, reported in 1899.³⁸ At the beginning of the 20th century, most of them left Romania for South America and Germany. In Constanta, at Viile Noi, a church had been formed, which at one point numbered 70 people, of which, in 1906, approximately 20 people remained.³⁹

Transylvania

The beginning of Adventism in Transylvania is linked to Louis Conradi. In 1890, he arrived in Cluj-Napoca in search of the old Sabbatarians, whom he had heard had kept the Sabbath before the Reformation.⁴⁰ Studying local archives and talking to people of culture, he learned of the existence

35 F. M. Wilcox, "The Work in Europe," *The Bible Echo* 9.36 (1894): 286.

36 L. R. Conradi, "The German-Russian Mission Field," *The Home Missionary* 6.11 (1894): 255-256.

37 Henry P. Holser, "Southern Europe," *Review and Herald* 75.44 (1898): 700.

38 L. R. Conradi, "The German Russian Fields. Rumania," *The Daily Bulletin of the General Conference* 8.6 (1899): 54.

39 L. R. Conradi, "Rumania and Austria-Hungary," *Review and Herald* 83.40 (1906): 13.

40 L. R. Conradi, "The German Mission Field," *Review and Herald*, 69.49 (1892): 773.

of three Sabbatarians in Beziadul Nou. To test whether they still observed the Sabbath, he visited one of them on the Sabbath itself. He was surprised by the way he was received; the man observed the Sabbath even though he was officially part of the Catholic Church. Because he was up to date with church taxes, the priest turned a blind eye to the Sabbath. However, shortly after he was welcomed into the house, they received a visit from the priest who told Conradi that proselytism was prohibited.⁴¹

In Cluj, Conradi met the family of Johann Rottmayer, one of the first Baptists in Transylvania who represented the British Bible Society. They would discuss the Advent message even after Conradi's departure. Following their correspondence, his wife and daughter would accept Adventism, and Rottmayer would later follow them. In November, Conradi returned to Cluj from where he would leave for Hamburg with Rottmayer's daughter, Marie. She would work on the Hungarian-language Bible materials and on the correspondence.⁴² Their impact was so great that the Synod of the Reformed Church had to take this issue seriously.⁴³

Rottmayer's wife gave some Adventist publications to Wilhelm Johannes Tentesch, a baker by trade, who would become the most effective evangelist with literature in Transylvania at that time. The result of the spread of Adventist literature was seen within nine years, when there were approximately 50 Adventists in Cluj-Napoca and the surrounding area.⁴⁴

However, the greatest impact on Adventism in Transylvania was made by John F. Huenergardt, a German born on December 25, 1875, in Russia, but whose parents emigrated to the USA when he was 9 months old. He will be known as coming from Kansas, USA. He becomes a pastor and in 1897 is sent by the General Conference as a missionary to Europe. After a two-month journey in Hamburg, where he works with enthusiasm, he is sent to Cluj to work together with Rottmayer. In nine months, he learns Hungarian to such an extent that it allows him to preach and converse. After only one year spent in Hungary (of which Transylvania was also part), he baptizes 53 people. Following some theological studies

41 L. R. Conradi, *Die Geschichte des Sabbats* (1912; reed., Ausgabe: Gihon Publishing, 2009), 458-459.

42 O. A. Olsen, "From the Filed. Hamburg, Germany," *Bible Echo* 6.21 (1891): 332.

43 L. R. Conradi, "The German Mission Field," *Review and Herald* 69.49 (1892): 773.

44 Gunter Gehan, *Întreita solie în Austro-Ungaria și România 1869-1938*, 60 și 71.

published at the Academy of Sciences in Budapest, he is elected a member of the academy.⁴⁵

As a result of missionary activity in Transylvania, at the beginning of the 20th century there were approximately 90 Adventists, most of them in Cluj-Napoca and its surroundings (approximately 50), the rest being in Arad, Sibiu, Fagaras, and Seica Mare. Although most of them were German and Hungarian speakers, there were also Romanian speakers among them.

Bucharest

The most significant impact on Adventism in Romania was played by the Adventist community in Bucharest. This would play a decisive role in the development of the Adventist Church in Romania.

The first missionary to arrive in Bucharest was the German Ferdinand Adomeit, around 1900. He did not know Romanian and as such he worked only with ethnic Germans. As a result of his work, Ana Klör was baptized, with whom he was able to dialogue and to whom he offered Adventist literature in German. He was later transferred to Sibiu.⁴⁶ Two years later, another German, Gerhard Perk, arrived, being the first ordained missionary pastor. Perk had worked as an agent of the British Bible Society in Russia and in this capacity had met Adventist literature. In 1886, he met Conradi, who called him to become an evangelist with literature. Perk accepted and became an Adventist. In Bucharest, he organized Bible conferences every Monday and Thursday. Following the activity of the two missionaries, Adomeit and Perk, a baptism was organized on October 18, 1902. The first reports confirm that we have 8 Adventists in Bucharest, in 1903. In total, there were 90 people in Romania who were part of four churches and groups.⁴⁷

In 1904, J. F. Hinter replaced Perk and organized the first Adventist group in Bucharest, which had 16 members. Among them were Nicolae Jelescu, an instrumentalist of the royal chapel, Petre P. Paulini, a medical student, and the officer Stefan Demetrescu. Two years later,

45 Gunter Gehan, *Întreita solie în Austro-Ungaria și România 1869-1938*, 69.

46 Dumitru Popa, *Biografii ale pionierilor Bisericii adventiste din România*, Vol. I, 679.

47 Guy Dail, "Austria, Hungary, and the Balkans," *Review and Herald* 80.28 (1903): 18.

Bucharest had 65 Adventists, a figure revealed by Louis Conradi. He had visited Bucharest that year, 1906. On that occasion, he was astonished to find that on his last visit he had found 25 members, and the meetings had been stopped by the police. Now, Hinter had rented a spacious hall, where he preached to an audience of 60-100 people. Pastor Hinter had already baptized 16 people, and more were coming. The number of members had increased from 25 to 65, and the meetings were no longer disturbed by the police.⁴⁸

Pastor Hinter's activity attracted the attention of the Romanian authorities, who were faced with the spread of new Christian religious beliefs. Their solution, the expulsion of Johann Hinter in 1909, did not produce the effect expected by the authorities. Romanian missionaries were encouraged to join the work, which led to an opening towards the native population.⁴⁹ This led to rapid growth of the church.

Romanian Adventism until 1946

The penetration of Adventism into Romanian territory was not without difficulties. On the one hand, the state of the population⁵⁰ full of superstitions stemming from an ignorance of the Bible and on the other hand, the reaction of the authorities or local leaders, such as priests, who restricted the freedoms of individuals, were the biggest problems that Romanian Adventism faced.

If in 1901, the number of members was only 70,⁵¹ despite the difficulties the number of Adventists increased, reaching at the end of the two world wars 13,373 members, located in 375 churches,⁵² that is, an increase

48 L.R. Conradi, "Rumania and Austria-Hungary," *Review and Herald* 83.40 (1906): 13.

49 Among them were Petre Paulini, Stefan Demetrescu, Constantin Popescu or Petre Paunescu, those who would become leaders of the work in Romania.

50 This state of the population led George Butler to be skeptical about the progress of Adventism in Romania. See George Butler, "Visit to Roumania," *Review and Herald* 61.21 (1884): 328-329.

51 L.R. Conradi, "Biennial Report of district. The European Conference," *The General Conference Bulletin* 4.6 (1901): 159.

52 "Southern European Division," *1946 YearBook of the Seventh-day Adventist Denomination*, editor Claude Conard (Washington, DC: Review and Herald Publishing Association), 208.

of over 190 times. The figures would probably have shown differently if the war and the territorial losses suffered by Romania had not occurred.

By law, the Ministry of Religious Affairs issued an operating permit for a local church. For this, four conditions had to be met. The first of these was that there had to be a group of at least 20 believers, who had to prove that they were not part of another religious cult. The second condition was proof that there was a place of worship. The third condition was proof that that place was located at a distance from another place of worship, to avoid mutual hostilities. The last condition was proof of the existence of a local cemetery. Of all the conditions, the first was the most difficult to achieve, due to the difficulty with which it could be proven that a person was not part of another religion. If he had left another church, he had to prove with documents, before the civil registrar, the cult he had left and the date. Also, all these data had to be certified by the local authorities.⁵³ All of these requirements were intended to try to

53 Art. 4. – For the authorization of a local religious association, the Ministry of Religious Affairs shall submit to the Ministry of Religious Affairs the request of a group of at least 20 believers, who meet the conditions and qualifications of art. 2 of this decision, proven by documents: (1). A table with the number, surname, first name, domicile, nationality, ethnic origin, marital status and confessional status of the members of the local association and indicating the cult abandoned and the date of abandonment. This table shall include at least 100 heads of families. The data in the table shall be endorsed and certified for accuracy by the local communal authority, which shall be given upon request any documents it deems necessary for official visa and certification. The columns in the table shall include the number, date of the documents and the authority that issued them. The confessional status shall be proven with the evidence of the civil status officer, provided for in art. 45, paragraph 5, of the law for the general regime of religions. Those who are members of a recognized religious association by birth shall prove their religious status with the official extract from their birth certificate. (2). Official proof from the competent authorities that they have their own premises for a house of prayer, which meets the sanitary conditions required by local health regulations. (3). Official proof that the premises intended for the house of prayer are located at a sufficient distance from the places of prayer of other religions, to avoid any mutual hostile manifestations. (4). Official proof that there is a communal cemetery in the locality or proof that religious associations have their own land for the establishment of their own cemetery, authorized by the communal and health authorities. The properties provided for in paragraphs 3 and 4 may be purchased in the name of an associate and made available to the local association by means of an authentic declaration. See Archives of the Conference Union of the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Romania, File A13/1938, no. 54. 73.

stop the development of other religious cults and implicitly the Adventist Church.

Despite the requirements imposed by the Ministry of Religious Affairs, Adventism spread to all regions of the country. In some places, the authorities issued the required documents, but in some areas the church encountered major problems. The 1930s revealed abuses by priests, gendarmes, or mayors. Thus, some of the people who had been issued a certificate of change of religion and who were baptized in the Adventist Church were called to the City Hall and their certificate was canceled.⁵⁴ At other times, the issuance of the certificate was conditional on paying the contribution to the parish from which he had left and the taxes to the state.⁵⁵ Priests were disrupting Adventist funerals, becoming recalcitrant or even violent, inciting others to violence. Unfortunately, these cases on the part of priests were not isolated.⁵⁶

Ministerial Decision No. 26208 of June 11, 1938, outlawed the Adventist Church. In fact, the document targeted the Reformed Adventist Church, but the decision was extended to include the Seventh-day Adventist Church as well.⁵⁷ The same decision prohibited both individual and collective religious proselytism. The local authority also had to annually verify the church membership register, and the preachers and leaders of each church had to be confirmed by the Ministry of Religious Affairs.⁵⁸

54 Archives of the Conference Union of the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Romania, File A17/1934, no. 16, 472-476.

55 Archives of the Conference Union of the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Romania, File A16/1935, 825.

56 Archives of the Conference Union of the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Romania, File A17/1934, no. 16, 240-242.

57 Art. 1. – Those religious associations which, through their doctrine and ritual practices, violate the laws of organization of the state and its institutions, and contravene good morals, public order and peace, are absolutely prohibited, under the penalty of the penalties provided for in the penal code and in the law for the defense of state order. The religious associations identified to date and whose existence or functioning is absolutely prohibited are: Millennial Associations (International Association of Bible Students, Jehovah's Witnesses, through the Bible and Tract Society or under any other religious or commercial name they may present themselves), Pentecostals, Tremorists, Apostolic Church of God, Penitents, Nazarenes, Reformed Adventists, Reapers, Hlists, Innocentists and Stylists. See Archive of the Conference Union of the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Romania, File A13/1938, no. 54, 73.

58 Archives of the Conference Union of the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Romania, File A13/1938, no. 54, 74.

Church leaders at the time filed a lawsuit to overturn the decision, arguing that the Seventh-day Adventist Church had been a religious association for some time. They also pointed out that preachers could not be required to function only within the house of worship, and they challenged the ban on proselytism as unconstitutional.⁵⁹ Unfortunately, nothing worked, so for a period, the Adventist Church operated illegally.

Conclusions

The Sabbatarian movement in Transylvania, which emerged during the Protestant Reformation, can be seen as a precursor to Adventism, through the observance of the biblical seventh-day Sabbath.

The first missionaries who arrived in Romanian territory came via the American route, most of them being of German origin, except for Michael Belina Czechowski, a former Catholic priest of Polish origin.

Louis Conradi, a German who also arrived in American territory, was impressed by the way an Adventist family lived their faith and after studying the Advent message, joined the church. Coming to Europe as a missionary, he had a significant impact on the development of Adventism in Transylvania and Dobrogea.

The expulsion by the authorities of the German-born pastor, Hinter, who worked in Bucharest, made the church think of a new strategy, namely, the training of Romanian pastors. This was the moment when Adventism exploded in Romania, with Bucharest becoming the focal point of the church.

The development was not easy, since a series of difficulties were encountered from the beginning. As in science, in religion the majority is not necessarily right. The history of Adventism in Romania has highlighted the fact that if the message of God, regardless of how it is understood by Christianity, is not evaluated impartially, based on a peaceful dialogue, it can provoke vehement and even violent reactions. Unfortunately, in the case of Romanian Adventism, such reactions attracted religious persecution not only from the authorities or the majority church, but also from Protestants who saw their religion threatened. Instead of

59 Archives of the Conference Union of the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Romania, File A14/1938, no. 55, 132-138.

resorting to biblical dialogue, they preferred forceful reactions, through which to shut the mouths of God's messengers.

Bibliography:

- ✦ BUTLER, George. "Foreign Travel – No. 14. Roumania." *Youth's Instructor* 32.34 (1884): 134-135.
- ✦ _____. "Visit to Roumania." *Review and Herald* 61.21 (1884): 328-329.
- ✦ BOURDEAU, A. C. „Beginning of Our Work in Roumania." *European Division Conference Review* 2.2 (1913): 34-36.
- ✦ _____. "Progress of the Cause. Roumania." *Review and Herald* 61.39 (1884): 620.
- ✦ _____. "Progress of the Cause. Roumania." *Review and Herald* 61.45 (1884): 715-716.
- ✦ CONRADI, L. R. „A Visit to Rumania." *Review and Herald* 69.2 (1892): 25-26.
- ✦ _____. "A Visit to Rumania." *Review and Herald* 71.20 (1894): 308.
- ✦ _____. "Begginnings of Our Works in Europe." *Adventist Review Anniversary Issue* 101.38 (1924): 14.
- ✦ _____. "Biennial Report of district. The European Conference." *The General Conference Bulletin* 4.6 (1901): 157-160.
- ✦ _____. *Die Geschichte des Sabbats*. 1912; reed., Ausgabe: Gihon Publishing, 2009.
- ✦ _____. "Rumania and Austria-Hungary." *Review and Herald* 83.40 (1906): 13.
- ✦ _____. "The Dragon's Voice in Rumania." *Review and Herald* 70.32 (1893): 506-507.
- ✦ _____. "The Evening Sermon." *General Conference Bulletin* 9.13 (1922): 318.
- ✦ _____. "The German Mission Field." *Review and Herald*, 69.49 (1892): 773.
- ✦ _____. "The German Russian Fields. Rumania." *The Daily Bulletin of the General Conference* 8.6 (1899): 54.
- ✦ _____. "The German-Russian Mission Field." *The Home Missionary* 6.11 (1894): 255-256.

- ✦ DAIL, Guy. "Austria, Hungary, and the Balkans." *Review and Herald* 80.28 (1903): 18.
- ✦ DÁN, Robert. *Matthias Veche-Glirius, Life and Work of a Radical Antitrinitarian with his Collected Writings*. Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó; Leiden: E.J. Brill, 1982.
- ✦ FIT'ZAI, Corneliu-Ghiocel. *Mișcarea adventistă de ziua a șaptea din România*. Pantelimon: Viața și Sănătate, 2018.
- ✦ GEHAN, Gunter. *Întreita solie în Austro-Ungaria și România 1869-1938*. Graphe, 2008.
- ✦ HOLSER, Henry P. "Southern Europe." *Review and Herald* 75.44 (1898): 700.
- ✦ LAND, Gary. *Historical Dictionary of the Seventh-day Adventists*. In *Historical Dictionaries of Religions, Philosophies, and Movements*, No. 56. Lanham, Maryland: The Scarecrow Press, 2005.
- ✦ OLSEN, O. A. "From the Filed. Hamburg, Germany." *Bible Echo* 6.21 (1891): 332.
- ✦ PÁKOZDY, Ladislaus M. *Der siebenbürgische Sabbatismus. Seine Entstehung und Entwicklung vom Unitarismus zum Judentum sowie sein Untergang*. Stuttgart: Kohlhammer, 1973.
- ✦ POPA, Dumitru. *Biografii ale pionierilor Bisericii adventiste din România*. Vol. I. Bucharest: Grafic Print, 1995.
- ✦ RIBTON, H. P. "Report from Egypt." *Review and Herald* 55.1 (1880): 13.
- ✦ ROTARU, Ioan-Gheorghe. *Sabatarieni în contextul vieții transilvănene (sec. XVI-XX). Aspecte din Istoria Sabatarianismului european și transilvănean*. Second edition, revised and added. Vol. II. Cluj-Napoca: Risoprint, 2019.
- ✦ ROTARU, Ioan-Gheorghe. "Soarta sabatarienilor transilvăneni care nu au trecut în anul 1866 la credința iudaică." *Studia Universitatis Babeș-Bolyai – Theologia Orthodoxa* 16.2 (2014): 119-134.
- ✦ WHITNEY, B. L. "Progress of the Cause. Report from Central European Mission." *Review and Herald* 61.1 (1884): 5.
- ✦ WILCOX, F. M. "The Work in Europe." *The Bible Echo* 9.36 (1894): 286.
- ✦ *1946 YearBook of the Seventh-day Adventist Denomination*. Editor Claude Conard. Washington, DC: Review and Herald Publishing Association.

- ✦ *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook 1885*. Battle Creek, MI: Seventh-day Adventist Publishing Association, 1885.
- ✦ *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook 1886*. Battle Creek, MI: Seventh-day Adventist Publishing Association, 1886.
- ✦ *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook 1887*. Battle Creek, MI: Seventh-day Adventist Publishing Association, 1887.
- ✦ *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook 1888* (Battle Creek, MI: Seventh-day Adventist Publishing Association, 1889).
- ✦ *Seventh-day Adventist YearBook of Statistics for 1889* (Battle Creek, MI: Seventh-day Adventist Publishing Association, 1989).
- ✦ Archive of the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Romania, Voluntari, Ilfov County.
- ✦ File A13/1938; File A14/1938; File A16/1935; File A17/1934